

HISTORICAL PEDAGOGICAL ASPECTS OF IMPROVING THE SYSTEM OF CONTINUOUS PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT OF TEACHERS AND ADVANCED FOREIGN EXPERIENCES

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***Abstract.** Today, the process of development of international relations clearly shows that establishing partnerships as the main form of cooperation and studying foreign experience on modernization of training systems is becoming a very urgent task. In many developed countries, continuous professional development is the main condition for improving the activity of the educational organization, and therefore the task of the leader is to provide the necessary conditions for this development. This article is devoted to the study and analysis of the international experiences of the developed countries of the world level of the system of continuous professional development in the education system.*

***Keywords:** continuous professional development system, foreign experiences, teacher training system, continuous education stages, students, teachers, modern educational technologies, software tools, educational tools, teacher training.*

Introduction. In a situation where the interconnection and interdependence of all countries of the world is expanding and deepening, the development of the system of professional development of pedagogical personnel in Uzbekistan cannot be studied separately from the processes of development of the world educational space. In many foreign countries, in the coordination of the UN, UNESCO, OECD (Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development), targeted scientific-research works on comparative pedagogy are being carried out in the field of teacher training. [10].

In many developed countries, continuous professional development is the main condition for improving the activity of the educational organization, and therefore the task of the leader is to provide the necessary conditions for this development. However, since the understanding of what teacher professional competence means differs significantly in different countries, the methods of ensuring it also differ [10].

Analysis of results. Professional development is considered an obligation of teachers in almost all European countries and regions. However, not all places have a regulatory framework that defines this responsibility. For example, in France, Iceland, the Netherlands and Sweden, in-service training is declared as a duty of teachers, but in practice they can avoid it. In Poland, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain and Luxembourg, continuing education is voluntary, but if not pursued, it affects the position and salary. In Luxembourg and Spain, teachers registered for a specific course of study receive an additional salary. In the remaining three countries, teachers accumulate credits for various forms and curricula, which are taken into account when they are appointed to a new position. In Cyprus, Greece and Italy, CPD is only the responsibility of primary school teachers. [17].

In the 60s of the twentieth century, in the USA, earlier than in other countries, they realized that social and technical progress depends primarily on the people themselves - how they are taught and brought up - in other words, how the school works and the professional skills of the teacher [43]. This is evidenced by the continuous school reforms implemented in this country since the 1960s. In the 80s of the 20th century, American experts in the field of teacher training came to the understanding that a skilled teacher should not only be proficient in pedagogical technologies, but also possess high personal, moral, intellectual, and social qualities. In this regard, the American teacher training system is aimed not only at providing teachers with additional modern knowledge, but also at stimulating their cognitive activity, creative research and personal growth [45].

The analysis of the processes of development of the teacher training system in the USA showed that the leaders of the political and business world of this country, earlier than in other countries, realized that an effective system of retraining and training of teachers is a necessary condition for long-term economic prosperity [45].

However, the progressive development of the US vocational training system has not been smooth or easy. It was a process full of changes involving different stages. Three stages can be conditionally distinguished among them: from the 40s to the 60s, from the 60s to the 80s of the 20th century, and from the 80s to the present day. Each stage of the development of the qualification system has its own characteristics, which are characterized by the specific characteristics of the socio-economic and cultural development of the country, and the demands of the society for the school.

The historical-pedagogical generalization of the problem allows to note the connections reflected in the studied approaches between the innovations characterizing the modern American school life and the content of teacher training. Despite their obvious differences, all of them are aimed at training a master teacher who not only skillfully masters modern pedagogical technologies, but also has high personal qualities and consciously participates in changing the school environment.

Based on the research conducted in the training system, American experts (A. Brolli, Ch. Knopper) [43] came to the following conclusions: the main link in the training system is the teacher; it is not promising to train a teacher in a one-sided special subject; a modern teacher must have perfect knowledge of pedagogical and social-psychological knowledge. These recommendations made it possible to take a number of practical measures to fundamentally improve the professional training of teachers.

In the early 2000s, when the No Child Left Behind Act in the United States introduced regular testing of teachers, it had a negative impact on the content and quality of teacher training programs, according to many researchers. They began to turn into training sessions on various strategies for passing the tests successfully, and the teacher's professionalism was almost ignored. In contrast, some researchers believe that continuous supervision has encouraged schools to turn to professional development, especially educational institutions that analyze and popularize best teaching practices. Some researchers note that teachers who want in-service training are generally already successful teachers, while weak teachers do not seek in-service training at all [21].

In England, with the transition from a centralized school effectiveness system to a decentralized school improvement system that seeks to address existing deficiencies in each

school, private education service providers are emerging to offer their development services to school communities. True, often they promise to quickly solve the most difficult problems and do not leave time to think about how and what children will learn. However, team professional development is certainly a prerequisite for the success of a school improvement program. This has been mentioned extensively in the works of Michael Fullan [22]. Analyzing the experience of England, he emphasizes that the professional development of the whole team is more effective if it is carried out in the school itself than individual training [23].

Much of the professional development of teachers in England and Wales takes place in the workplace. This involves not only a comprehensive effort to improve school performance, but also the professional collaboration of teachers, students and parents in this process to bring different perspectives, to share knowledge and skills, focused on the development of each class and student. Such programs arose out of theories about the conditions under which successful teacher development can occur. According to them, teacher development can be successful - if they:

- to pay attention to the teaching process and the results of students in the environment and conditions in which they teach;
- to have the opportunity to learn and experiment for a long time, and at the same time to receive feedback on the implemented innovations from colleagues, students and their parents;
- have the opportunity to get help from experts both inside and outside the school, as well as to get acquainted with the results of modern research [24].

In half of the countries surveyed by TALIS, there is no minimum time limit for teacher professional development. In countries where such requirements exist - some Australian states, Austria, Belgium, Finland, Hungary, the Netherlands, Scotland, Switzerland, Sweden, and French communities in some US states - the minimum period is usually five days a year. But there are also hourly deadlines: in Austria, the minimum duration of the advanced training course is 15 hours per year, in Sweden - 104 hours [11]. Time standards have recently been introduced in England and Wales. Now, every teacher is obliged to devote at least 5 days a year to professional development, and the school can finance up to 18 such professional development days. In the Czech Republic, teachers are paid 12 days of independent work per year to organize their professional development. Due to the flexibility of school schedules in Italy, in-service training is usually done during teachers' free time. Often these intensive trainings are of a collective nature and last for several days. In addition, the teacher's contract states that he can allocate 5 school days free from classes to participate in other activities. In Lithuania, Finland and Slovenia, a teacher is legally entitled to 5 days of tuition per year. In Romania, Belgium and Luxembourg, the teacher is paid for the time spent in the weekly methodical training sessions. In Portugal, the teacher is paid by the employer for up to 10 hours of voluntary training in addition to 3 to 8 days of mandatory professional development.

In England, the Teacher Training Agency has been transformed into the Training and Development Agency, tasked with creating new versions of professional standards and developing training programs that reflect the main priorities of education policy.

In most European countries, continuing education programs for teachers are free. In Hungary, 80% of the cost of such programs is covered by the state, and 20% by schools and teachers themselves. In Finland, for example, the government spends 220-250 million euros a year on such programs, but schools pay for travel and teacher replacements themselves.

Therefore, Finnish teachers often apply to public and private foundations for study grants. In the Czech Republic, the Netherlands, England and Lithuania, funding for professional development is transferred entirely to schools, and schools themselves decide to whom and how to provide development opportunities.

Most OECD member countries have initial training programs for aspiring teachers. Ten of the twenty-four countries have made participation in these programs mandatory. These are Australia, England, Northern Ireland, Wales, France, Israel, Italy, Japan, South Korea and Switzerland. Participation in such programs is voluntary in Scotland, and in Quebec (Canada), Denmark, the Netherlands, and Sweden, the school decides independently whether to participate in these programs. In Israel, Japan, Northern Ireland and Switzerland, vocational training programs are run jointly by teacher training institutes and schools. The duration of the programs varies from seven to eight months (Korea and Greece) to two years (Quebec, Switzerland and some US states). Mentors and school leaders are involved in the organization of such programs.

Ideas for mass retraining of large groups of teachers, as in Sweden, are also popular in former union countries. For example, in Kazakhstan, mass retraining of all teachers by 2020 has been set as a task, and 10 priority development directions have been selected, mainly determined by the European Union.

Although professional development is taken into account in the certification of Russian teachers, this does not directly affect salary increases, Kazakhstan and Georgia provide salary increases for professional development. They believe that the lack of real benefits negatively affects the motivation of Russian teachers to improve their skills.

Teacher training in Germany is carried out on the basis of training institutes in each federal state. Such a regional structure provides feedback and implementation of specific goals that enable the coordination of the activities of these institutions. It is a very important principle that regions are given independence in the organization of professional development, according to which each school annually submits a plan of measures for professional development to the district administration.

In Finland, teachers are well trained in research methods and teaching practice. Therefore, they are experts with modern diagnostic skills and work together to provide training that meets the needs of the students and the subject being taught as a team [38].

In Finland, employers (school principals or regional committees) are responsible for organizing in-service training for teachers every year.

Finland does not have a specialized training system for school principals, as the selection of candidates for this position requires principals to be persons who have proven themselves to have the necessary professional qualities. If necessary, directors undergo consulting practice in courses organized by municipalities or are trained in various seminars on management, personnel management, psychological support of the climate in the team and other aspects of modern management. Finland has a very developed system of professional associations of partners and school leaders, as well as a developed system of sharing innovative experiences.

Singapore has implemented a consistent and comprehensive system for evaluating the quality of teaching and teacher development [38].

Given the importance of teacher training in South Korea, a law was passed in the mid-1960s to establish training centers for elementary and middle school teachers.

In 1992, secondary school teacher training institutes were opened under 17 universities. Similar primary school teacher training institutes were opened in 11 state teacher training colleges [38].

In Japan, the teacher development system (INSET) is divided into two categories, one is compulsory and the other is voluntary. Voluntary extra-curricular activities, in turn, are divided into in-school and out-of-school education. Compulsory in-service training is usually carried out at teacher training centers located in each prefecture [38].

The degree of study of the study. In our republic, the training system (MOT) began to be formed in the 30s of the last century. Relatively little information is given in studies about the history of the development of this system. The establishment of a system of retraining and professional development of pedagogic personnel in our country based on the researches of our country's scientists J.G'. and it is possible to comment on the history of its development.

In our country, there are various options for the periodicization of the formation of the teacher training system. The most detailed analysis of formation and periodization J.G. Yuldoshev, H.Q. Yuldoshev, N.A. Lukina, E.M. Nikitin and P.V. It is mentioned in Khudominsky's works.

From 1917 to the 80s of the 20th century, the first historical-pedagogical work on the formation, development and improvement of the system of improving the qualifications of public education workers was carried out by P.V. Khudominsky [80]. It defines specific periods of the formation of the state system of professional development in the former union, including Uzbekistan, which are directly related to the stages of development of public education. Trends in the development of the teacher training system E.M. It is also covered in Nikitin's works [79]. The periodization given by him takes into account not only the historical stages of the formation of the training system associated with the development of the general education school, but also the impact of such events in the life of the country, for example, collectivization of the country, industrialization of the economy, etc. This periodization problem was also focused on in the researches of N.A. Lukin [78].

In the 20s and 30s of the 20th century, the planning and full coverage of the state system of teacher training and retraining; continuity of the professional development process throughout the teacher's career; the connection between professional development and the tasks facing the school; basic principles such as the relationship between courses and other forms of professional development, while encouraging teachers' creative research and the leading role of self-education [79].

The next stage, in 1930-1950, is characterized by the restructuring of the educational system and the implementation of universal primary education. Many teachers did not have special pedagogical knowledge and had to attend courses at local public education departments. Pedagogical offices have become the main organizational form of methodological activity in order to provide comprehensive support to teachers. In some regions, pedagogical laboratories were established under the departments of public education, which were later reorganized as teacher training institutes. It was during this period - on the basis of the training course for primary school students at that time, the first retraining and retraining educational institution in our country was established under the name of the Institute for the Improvement of Qualifications of Public Education Personnel (now - the head of the public education system named after A. Avloni and the institute of retraining and advanced training of specialist

employees) was established. Later, teacher training institutes were established in the Republic of Karakalpakstan (1936), Bukhara (1947), Samarkand (1944) and Fergana (1945) regions.

Thus, by the end of the 40s, in general, a network of state institutions for teacher training was formed, its organizational foundations and the structure of methodological service were defined.

By the beginning of the 50s, the state system of teacher training was developed. At the moment, the continuous quantitative growth and quality change of the system components (institutions, organizational forms, content) of this system's activity; expansion and strengthening of relations between them; the country has a stable view of its own characteristics, such as the implementation of the state order set out in the directives and regulations on the development of education and teacher training.

Thus, in the period from 1917 to 1950, there was a gradual development and stabilization of the training system: constant quantitative growth and qualitative change of the components of the system (network of institutions, organizational forms, content); expansion and strengthening of relations between them; implementation of the state order specified in the instructions and regulatory documents on the development of education in the country and the improvement of the qualifications of the teaching staff. Since then, the organizational structure and forms of professional development of professors and teachers in our country have remained unchanged.

1950-60 years (the third stage) was the stage of creative analysis and improvement of the educational system. During this period, the number of teacher training institutes expanded in our country, including in 1952, teacher training institutions started their activities in 4 regions - Andijan, Kashkadarya, Surkhondarya and Khorezm regions, in 1955, in Tashkent region and in 1957, teachers of Tashkent city had their own training institutes. Since 1959, methodological rooms have been operating in educational departments, and their recommendations are aimed at improving the methods of educational work and labor education. Structural changes were made in teacher development institutes to meet the new needs of the Soviet school: boarding schools, evening schools, primary military training, leading personnel, educational affairs, pedagogy and psychology offices, and the exchange of advanced pedagogical experiences were introduced.

–In the fourth stage (from the end of the 1960s to the beginning of the 1980s), the transition to the general secondary education system was carried out on the basis of the idea of comprehensive development and improvement of the quality of work of all levels of the educational system, as it became clear that secondary schools could not meet the requirements of the scientific and technical revolution and the preparation of graduates for life. The polytechnicization of the general education school created the need to attract highly qualified scientific personnel and the best teachers from higher educational institutions to the system of highly qualified personnel training, which expanded the scope of activities of teacher training institutes for mass retraining of personnel.

–It was during this period that teacher training institutes were established in a number of other regions of our country - Syrdaryo (1964), Namangan (1967) and Jizzakh (1974) regions.

–At the next stage, in the mid-80s of the twentieth century, researchers paid attention to the expansion of the tasks and functions of the professional development system, the need to master the general concept of accumulated advanced pedagogical experience. The task of

optimizing and intensifying the educational process was assigned to the educational system. This led the training system to solve problems at the technological level.

–The next stage of our research is the 90s. The twentieth century is characterized by the process of modernization of education in our country, which was reflected in the adoption of the main state normative document - the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" in 1997 [88]. In this regard, teacher development institutes were reorganized as educational staff training and retraining institutes. The reason for this was the complexity of the structure of school education due to the emergence of new types of educational institutions - lyceums, gymnasiums, private schools.

–The training system is the main source of acquiring new information, knowledge, skills and qualifications by pedagogues and leaders, therefore, this system is, in a certain sense, responsible for the readiness of the education system employees for the modernization processes implemented in the field and therefore deserves special attention.

–The fact that all conditions have been created for the effective functioning of this system in our country is reflected in the regulatory and legal documents adopted in the field of education. Resolution No. 25 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 16, 2006 "On further improvement of the system of retraining and professional development of pedagogues" is of particular importance among these documents [91; 92; 93].

–According to H.Q. Yoldoshev, it is appropriate to organize the training system based on the following:

–identification and implementation of new pedagogical technologies and innovative methods in advanced education;

–by connecting pedagogues to training institutes remotely, improving the content of education, providing news on new methods of science and teaching;

–improvement of the system of continuous professional development of teachers by district (city) methodological offices from course to course;

–professors-teachers of departments and departments of professional development institutes and proposed lecturers should fundamentally revise the content, scientific-methodical orientation of the educational programs, lectures, and organize opportunities for their transmission through ICT tools [96, pp. 7-11].

–S.T.Turgunov said that to increase the efficiency of training processes, it is necessary to take into account the following:

–this process should have a research and analytical direction;

–taking into account the model of an expert personality in the development of the system of knowledge, skills and qualifications;

–use of modern pedagogical technologies in the educational process;

–creating a reflexive educational environment that ensures mutual creative cooperation of teachers and students;

–development of subject-subject relations;

–creating the necessary psychological environment to improve the personal capabilities of the participants of the educational process;

–creating conditions for students to choose teaching methods and forms, assignments;

–creating necessary conditions for differentiated methods and forms of teaching.

In the socio-economic life of our country, the reforms that began in 2017 have started a period of renewal in the education system, including the system of improving the qualifications of public education workers.

Comprehensive reforms are being implemented in the education system of our country under the direct leadership of President Sh. Mirziyoyev. These reforms cover all parts of the continuous education system established in our country, including the general secondary education system, and aim to bring school education up to world standards while eliminating the problems accumulated in the system over the years. A number of decisions and decrees adopted by our honorable president are aimed at developing the general secondary education system, raising the authority of teachers and trainers, and improving the quality of education in schools. It is attracting our children to give them a decent education.

In general, through the analysis of pedagogical, psychological, philosophical, scientific literature and scientific-research works on improving the qualification of pedagogic staff of general secondary schools, we found out that there are the following problems:

1. general secondary educational institutions have not developed the qualification of pedagogic personnel, pedagogical conditions have not been provided;
2. Pedagogical strategy for improving the qualification of pedagogical personnel of general secondary educational institutions has not been developed;
3. in the digital educational environment, general secondary education institutions have not modeled the improvement of the pedagogic personnel's qualifications;
4. the technology for improving the qualifications of school teachers in the digital educational environment is not improved;
5. The mechanisms for evaluating the levels of advanced training of teachers of general secondary schools have not been improved.

The solutions to the above-mentioned problems will be discussed in detail in the next chapters of the dissertation.

Summary. The advanced foreign experiences on improving the qualifications of teaching staff of general secondary educational institutions were analyzed. In particular, the training system of USA, England, Japan, South Korea, Singapore, Finland and many other countries with developed economic and educational system was studied and compared with the system of training in our country. In addition, the historical aspects of improving the qualifications of pedagogues in our country were mentioned in several stages. Existing problems in our country regarding skill development have been identified.

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